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**GAMIFICATION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UKRAINE:
DIFFICULTIES IN APPLYING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND POSSIBLE
WAYS TO RESOLVE THE PROBLEM
ГЕЙМІФІКАЦІЯ ОСВІТНЬОЇ СИСТЕМИ В УКРАЇНІ: ТРУДНОЩІ
ІМПЛЕМЕНТАЦІЇ ЗАРУБІЖНОГО ДОСВІДУ Й МОЖЛИВІ ШЛЯХИ
ВИРІШЕННЯ ПРОБЛЕМИ**

Abstract. Of this paper based on positive and negative results from the application of gamification techniques in the developed countries problem areas of this phenomenon are determined, and described possible directions for its use in Ukraine.

Keywords: gamification, modern technologies, education system, teacher, student.

Анотація. На підґрунті врахування позитивних та негативних результатів від впровадження гейміфікації в економічно розвинених державах виокремлено проблемні поля цього феномену, а також вказано на можливі напрями його імплементації в Україні.

Ключові слова: гейміфікація, сучасні технології, освітня система, викладач, студент.

It is hardly possible to imagine the life of a modern person without technological innovations. They make it more diversified and multifaceted and allows resolving the assigned tasks.

In the educational sphere (as well elsewhere), the solution of arising problems is closely connected to external and internal factors. If external factors are viewed as socio-economic, political, demographic, organizational, the internal ones, in most cases, are motivational and behavioral factors [10] (Zabalandikoetxea, S. U., Merino, J.D.G., 2013).

The combination of these factors strongly influences the efficiency of any process. In the field of education, the effectiveness of training and upbringing

processes depends directly on external and internal conditions. However, in our work we focus on a group of motivational and behavioral factors that determine the nature of the interaction between participants of the educational process (students and teachers).

In this context, a lot depends on the quality of professional training of the teacher himself, his use of modern methods and educational techniques. The teacher's background preparation and motivation for further personal and professional growth will contribute greatly to developing students' ability to find ways to resolve problems in their future professional activities in a rapidly developing world.

That is why we consider introduction of modern teaching methods as a necessary condition for further professional development and improvement of teachers and students. These techniques include gamification method, the use of which makes it possible to increase the efficiency of the educational process.

The aim of this paper is to determine based on positive and negative results from the application of gamification techniques in the developed countries problem areas of this phenomenon, and to describe possible directions for its use in Ukraine.

Methods: collection and analysis of sources for a particular problem.

Researchers classify the gamification method as a modern teaching method in secondary and higher education. It is in great demand due to its features: the intellectual activity of trainees, the development of creative thinking skills in the process of solving problems, a quick response to the situation, obtaining necessary skills and experience of action, guarantees of a quick feedback [2; 7; 8] (Connolly, T. M., Boyle, E., & Hailey, T., 2007; Nicholson, S., 2015; Seaborn, K., & Fels, D. I., 2015).

As evidenced by the works of teachers and researchers involved in the introduction of gamification into the educational process in secondary and high schools the potential of educational games in the digital format is quite high [1; 6] (Attali, Y., & Arieli-Attali, M., 2015; Nevin, C. R. et al., 2014).

This type of modern games has a strong impact on both the psychological and emotional sphere of users (motivation, the ability to empathize and support members of the game team) and the cognitive sphere of the development of students in exploring, absorbing and using the materials under study.

The results of this impact can be positive and negative. In most cases, researchers describe the positive effects of using digital games [5] (Krause, M., Mogalle, M., Pohl, H., & Williams, J. J. (2015). Among the negative impacts, they emphasize the formation of various types of addiction [9] (Weinstein, A. et al., 2015).

The analysis of data on the topic under study [3; 4] (Connolly T. M. et al., 2012: 663; Ke, F. 2009) made it possible to identify problem areas of the phenomenon of gamification:

- categorization of basic concepts of gamification in the scientific discourse;
- attempts to classify educational games and assign them to a certain type;

- attempts to establish and to measure the effects of entertaining games, which have a learning content;
- fragmented performance measurement (formation and improvement of various types of skills) from the game;
- criteria for the diversity of models for evaluating digital games.

Difficulties surrounding the above-mentioned processes force researchers in developed countries to move towards their solution by participating in the work of international gaming associations (NASAGA – North American Simulation and Gaming Association; SAGANET – Simulation and Gaming Association – The Netherlands; JASAG – Japanese Association of Simulation and Gaming; SSAGSg – Society of Simulation and Gaming of Singapore; SAGSAGA – Swiss-Austrian-German Simulation and Gaming Association). Their activity is aimed at studying and promoting the phenomenon of games, acquiring skills to create them, as well as to further improve the experience of using them by means of communication at international forums and conferences.

For Ukrainian researchers, the process of applying the latest experience has difficulties due to the following:

- lack of a clear algorithm for building games;
- focus on the experience of foreign researchers, where the digital games industry has a strong economic component;
- lack of close relationship with business – potential consumers of this format of educational games;
- lack of organizations that would operate on an All-Ukrainian scale to promote and subsequently develop digital games for schoolchildren, students and other types of users;
- low interest in the interaction of representatives of various professional communities (teachers, psychologists, game designers, engineers) due to lack of a single center that would streamline their efforts;
- lack of monitoring the needs of users of different age groups that may be interested in digital educational games of a particular type.

Conclusions. With these issues in mind, we focused on possible ways to resolve them in Ukraine:

- searching for people interested in creating a gaming association operating on an All-Ukrainian scale;
- attracting state owned and private organizations to cooperate in creating digital games;
- joining the efforts of professionals involved in formal and non-formal education to popularize the phenomenon of gamification by organizing online seminars and lectures, trainings, summer schools, conferences, short-term training courses for teachers to develop and model games;
- creation of developers' courses and special courses in the system of formal and non-formal education;

- promotion of developers' games based on the observance of copyright for intellectual property;
- involving university students into the research work through their participation in projects aimed at creating digital educational games during the study of humanities and natural sciences;
- developing games in the framework of interfaculty disciplines in higher education institutions.

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